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ASSESSMENT OF THE SUSTAINABILITY OF URBAN ENVIRONMENTS WITH A FOCUS ON SUSTAINABLE URBAN GROWTH

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Abstract: There is an emphasis on environmental sustainability assessment since it is regarded as one of the most crucial tools in the planning process for sustainable development. Planning and politics are unavoidable. It is considering the swift alterations that have transpired in numerous Iranian cities. The assessment of cities' ecological sustainability concerning appropriate urban planning has been ongoing for the past ten years. Additionally, given the fluctuations in the natural environment, it appears necessary. Appropriate study methodology and research design. The work approach is analytical and descriptive, using the same methodology to evaluate the environmental sustainability of the entire city with a focus on it. It's a facet of environmentally friendly growth. The study's findings demonstrated that the city is subject to the rule of law. There are signs of unsustainability that suggest this tendency will continue in the upcoming years due to the province's climate and the ongoing process. It will enlarge the city and create as much instability as possible throughout. The issue is durability; sustainable development will have no value regardless of cities and villages. The world is becoming more unstable, and urban and global sustainability are intellectual constructs. A city inhabited by people. Its primary sources of pollution include manual labor and overuse of contaminated areas, including noise pollution from irrigation systems, surface water and drinking water contamination, and more. The entrances now. Cities and households, pollutants and chemicals, surplus solid waste, and chemical and microbiological leaks into water sources. One of the most significant environmental risks to the city is garbage disposal, recycling, and health concerns. They show up. No all-encompassing program was in place to safeguard water resources, particularly regarding aquaculture and harvesting techniques. One of the most significant environmental hazards in cities is urban catastrophes.

Keywords: Environment, Sustainable Urban Development, Sustainability, Climate Change.

1. Introduction

The process of development without environmental planning in our country, located in the dry and semi-dry areas of the world, has faced widespread destruction and environmental pollution. Of course, to deal with the current crises and disruptions, the future of this land will be very worrying. To preserve the environment and comply with the Sustainable Development Goals, as well as the guidance and logical management of plans and projects, must be considered seriously because reducing the negative environmental impacts of activities in various branches is one of the essential elements of sustainability and sustainable development. Biology has been a significant concern since the late twentieth century [1].

Urban spaces have problems such as low environmental quality, noise, and air pollution. Recent criticism from urban researchers and human communities emphasized the concept of livability as one of the approaches to achieving a viable and quality urban environment. Their primary goal was to improve the quality of urban spaces on a human scale in modern cities [2]. Since then, the widespread wave of the township and its problems have increasingly increased the importance of livability and made it difficult and impossible to overcome. Annual meetings focused on the subject have been held since the 1970s, and organizations have also promoted it through local and state planning [3].

The main themes of this movement are the development of cities with walking capabilities, the development of mixed and multi-purpose applications, and the creation of a domain for the diversity of urban public facilities to make urban environments more viable and attractive. Ecologists have been inspired by the writings of 20th-century urban thinkers and humanists such as Lewis Mumford, Williams Nick, and Bernard Rudowsky [4].

Environmental Sustainability Assessment refers to material and non-material actions that provide crucial information on environmental impacts, compliance, stakeholder relations, and organizational systems and are indicators of the effectiveness and efficiency of actions taken in the environment.

This type of assessment emphasizes the positive and negative effects of the design on the environment. Specialists use it to describe and analyze the major effects of environmental activities to minimize the adverse effects by identifying influential factors in the environmental impact.

The emphasis on capacity land is a region for the human society that is sustainable at the maximum level of resource consumption and output and purification specifically in an area, specific planning without disturbance, deterioration of integrity, ecological unity, and bio-efficiency [5].

In Iran, the trouble is also felt in three theoretical areas among teachers and students in programming and design and, ultimately, policymakers and urban managers as a task more than ever. It is worth noting that the last five years of academic studies in sustainability in our country have been more focused on rural areas and large cities.

Today, urban tissues are the root of many pressures and contradictions on the development path, so many adaptations to the social and economic conditions of the time are not present, and lack of adequate access to the current standards of living, lack of livelihood, and biodiversity is one of their fundamental and major problems [6].

Despite the rotation of urban development policy patterns in the last decade from horizontal development to investment in urban tissue, the biosystem of these tissues has faced disruption and inefficiency both structurally and because of the functioning of vital components. In the meantime, identifying and assessing citizens' needs and mental and biological demands and adapting the appropriate conditions of these settlements will enhance the quality of mental satisfaction in urban areas and provide a framework for sustainable development [7].

The results of the livability of urban spaces Studies can help evaluate policies, rank locations, formulate urban management and planning strategies, and facilitate the study and prioritization of community issues for urban planners and managers to improve citizens' quality of life.

Livability findings can also be used to reflect on past political strategies and design future planning policies; in addition, bioscience studies can help identify problematic areas, the causes of people's discomfort, citizens' priorities in life, the impact of population social factors on biodiversity and promote and evaluate the work of policies and strategies in the field – quality of life [8].

Finally, it can be said that the use and application of the concept of quality of life is an argument against developing an economic future at the national level, a purely urban-scale development, and an attempt to qualitative criteria in the planning field [9].

2. Background

Research findings show that they are in a more favorable position in terms of environmental sustainability, so awareness of the ecological sustainability status of different urban areas and recognition of the existing situation can play an essential role in advancing management and planning and optimizing resource allocation to improve the well-being of residents and solve their problems [10].

They found that they needed policies to focus activities and change policies. Self-development-based development is an effort to stabilize the old residents of the renovation area, improve the quality of neighborhood services and such cases, and improve the quality of life in this part of the city [7].

In today's circumstances, most cities worldwide agree on the importance and necessity of recognizing, analyzing, and defining urban sustainability in various dimensions. Still, no consensus exists on its definitions, principles, criteria, and indicators. The main reason for this can be the direct dependence of this concept on local conditions, when and most importantly,

the social-economic bed and management of society knew the goal [11].

Research by Jacqueline de Chazal also defined the time frame as the most crucial after-imaginary framework for defining the meaning of each of these concepts. He thus said: Bio satisfaction is the state of desires about the satisfaction of living in a particular place for an individual or a group of people now, but persistence is the capacity to fulfill wishes for a person or group over time [12].

In Australia, to improve the impact of coherent urban shape on the eco-friendliness of face stores, it has been concluded that biodiversity in the two suburbs is similar in some cases and different in others.

Therefore, attention to the local conditions of each neighborhood plays a vital role in planning [13].

The Ten Principles for Vital Cities are defined as follows:

First: Planning for long-term reconstruction and growth.

Second: Accepting diversity.

Third: Approaching nature to people.

Fourth: Developing neighborly units.

Fifth: Creating public spaces.

Sixth: Establishing transportation and structures suitable for integration.

Seventh: Adjusting Density with Diversity and Green Borders.

Eighth: Activating Spaces for More Security.

Ninth: Strengthening New and Indigenous Roads.

Tenth: Enhancing the Principle of Participation with the Connection of Government, Private Sector, and Citizens [14].

The Australian article seeking to conduct this research identified 11 general areas of communication, social health, and well-being. Their relationship with health and welfare was confirmed, which included crime and security, education, employment and income, health and social services, housing, entertainment and culture, local food and other goods, the natural environment, public space, transportation, and social integration and local democracy [15].

3. Research Method

The type of applied research and the research method depends on the nature of the work of the descriptive-analytical method. Accordingly, the technique is used to assess the environmental sustainability of the whole city, with an emphasis on achieving sustainable development.

3.1. Theory of Research

Sustainability assessment reflects measurement and is increasingly becoming essential for changing conditions towards sustainable development. Sustainability assessment is a tool that

enables decision-makers and policymakers to take appropriate action to sustain as many societies as possible. The purpose is to evaluate its durability and to ensure the participation of optimum plans and activities in sustainable development [16].

Bioscientific Impact Assessment is a method for gaining confidence in decisions that may significantly impact the environment. It evaluates the environmental impact of different aspects of the environment; life is related to decisions and policies [17].

Environmental Sustainability Assessment refers to material and intangible measures that provide crucial information on environmental impacts, compliance, stakeholder relations, and organizational systems and indicate the effectiveness and efficiency of measures taken in the environment [18].

This type of assessment emphasizes the positive and negative effects of design on the environment. It is a way for specialists to describe and analyze the major effects of environmental activities to minimize the adverse effects by identifying influential factors in environmental impact.

The topic of emphasis in this context is the regional retention capacity for the human society that is sustainable at the maximum level of resource consumption and output and purification, specifically in a region, specific planning without disturbance, undermining integrity, ecological unity, and bio-efficiency [5].

Environmental sustainability assessment includes an assessment of the project's direct environmental impacts, including obstacles and efforts to reduce the harmful ecological implications [19].

Sustainability assessment is increasingly influenced by assessment tools that can be used as sustainable development assessment frameworks. Assessment frameworks are practical and helpful in choosing appropriate and efficient tools and their ease of use [20].

Assessment frameworks are used, on the one hand, to examine different aspects of policy to control sustainable change and, on the other hand, to guide the implementation of comprehensive and integrated assessment.

The study noted four categories of framework assessments: the environmental impact assessment (EIA), the Environmental Assessment (SEA), the Impact Assessment (IA), and the Durability Evaluation (ISA).

Table 1. Environmental sustainability indicators [21].

System	Main dimensions	Component	Criterion	Indicator
				land-use change
			Land	Lands contaminated by waste materials
				The amount of waste produced (Daily/ Ton)
		Land Resources		Satisfaction with drinking water quality

Environmental sustainability	Environment Resources and services	Resources Water	Discharging human and industrial wastes into open and surface waters	
			Prevention of water pollution	
		Air Quality	The concentration of pollutants in the air	
			Pollutant concentration in the air	
		Quality Landscape	Landscapes with natural value	
			Credits spent on protecting valuable landscapes	
			Destruction of beautiful landscapes (by changing uses)	
			Landscapes capable of tourism	
		Ecosystem Sensitive	Population density in coastal areas	
			Adherence to the care of the residential environment	
			Land use changes in coastal areas	
			The amount of discharge of sewage and waste materials to coastal areas	
	Credits spent on beach cleanups			
	Management of coastal areas			
	Environment Health	Environment Hygiene	Waste management	Satisfaction with waste disposal
			Sewage system management	Satisfaction with sewage disposal
		Environment Vulnerability	Natural hazards	Resistance of housing and buildings against earthquakes
				Flood prevention program
	Energy	Resources Energy	Energy consumption	The amount of carrier energy consumption (Electricity)
				The amount of carrier energy consumption (water)
The amount of carrier energy consumption (Gas)				
The amount of carrier energy consumption (Gasoline fuel)				
Carrier energy consumption costs				

3.2. Livability

What is livability? What are the characteristics of an eco-friendly city? In many texts, biodiversity and quality of life are expressed synonymously. The quality of life experienced by city citizens is filled with their ability to access transportation, communications, water and waste, food, clean air, cheap housing, efficient employment, green spaces, and parks.

Also, a city's ecological level is determined by how and how much its inhabitants participate in deciding to meet their needs. Biology is defined as the quality of life experienced by the inhabitants of a city or region.

In such lands, sustainability is the opportunity to enhance the quality of life we value [22]. You could say the first concept of biology is named Biological Streets.

It was presented by Donald Appleyard in 1981. However, Alan Jacobs sets out seven critical goals for the future of an excellent urban environment:

- (1) Livability.
- (2) Identity and control.
- (3) Access to opportunity, creativity, and enjoyment.
- (4) Health and purpose.
- (5) Cohabitation and public life.
- (6) Confidence in one's abilities.
- (7) A City That's Open to All. In other theories, bioscience means that we treat ourselves as citizens.

The concept of biological resilience of the decade 1980, the continued growth of the movement from the center cities, and the creation of spiritless suburbs in new urban development are now standard. The term "biodiversity" has officially entered urban literature since Susan and Henry Lannard published the book *Living Cities* in 1987.

Bio sensitivity to an urban system where the social, mental, and mental health of all people are concerned, they are shooting. This quality is about desirable urban spaces that reflect cultural richness. The fundamental principles that support this concept include equality, equity, accessibility, liberation, participation, and empowerment.

3.3. Environmental Challenges

In a broad statement, the environmental challenges in Iranian cities could be essentially the result of human activities; they are debatable on three levels: those that have had an international headquarters and are even created in the process of globalization.

This process has led to global warming and pollution of the earth's air, soil, and water, and its effects threaten all human communities and habitats. At the second level, they are placed in the framework of policies and operations, government and private sector are defined at the national level.

These include economic, social, and environmental policies, national designs, conventions, and architectural and urban regulations. Finally, specific environmental conditions, historical background, population, and management practices are at the third level, local.

3.4. Environmental Challenges at a Global Level

Today, major urban environmental concerns and issues are caused by political, economic, and social relations and relationships between different regions and countries. The growth of the population due to the natural increase in the world population and the decline in the population of the cities, and in particular the urban population of countries in the development of smaller cities and rural areas, has sought new needs and needs and

consequently consumed more and more irreplaceable natural resources and energy consumption. In Table 2, environmental challenges are presented at the global and national levels.

Table 2. Environmental issues, requirements, and repercussions at the national and global levels [23].

Consequences	Geographical scope	Dealer and necessities
Development of science and technology and communication	Development of industries and more production	The spread of soil, water, and air pollution
Expanding social and economic relations	Expansion of means of transportation	Destruction of agricultural land
	Development of communication channels for consumerism	Reduction of water resources
	Improving health and nutrition conditions	Consumption of mineral resources
	Population increases	
Regional and international wars and conflicts	Use of Weapons	Destruction of forests and pastures
How to manage and the efficiency of the rules	Unstable conditions in government systems	Destruction of natural landscapes and landscapes
	Renovation and reconstruction	Climate change
	Development of the tourism industry.	Pollution noise.
	Mismanagement and lack of efficient program.	Psychological and social injuries. Increase in physical illness.

3.5. Environmental Challenges at the National Level.

Among the most essential disturbances in developing countries over the past half-century is the increase in the general population, especially in our cities. Population growth in these countries, where the use of advanced technologies and programs to control and monitor the production and use of natural resources is facing problems and limitations, is doubling.

The overall population growth in countries doubles the need for energy and fossil fuels. The necessity of housing, foundations, side, and services for residents has led to the expansion of the construction of facilities that quickly occupy the surrounding environments of the residences.

The expansion of polluting industries, especially in urban areas, the excessive use of personal cars, and the harvesting of beaches, forests, and natural resources through private and government sectors to expand the tourism industry is causing severe damage to water, sanitation, and air resources. In particular, the mismanagement and inefficiency of programs and plans, as well as regulatory limitations and vice versa, may add unlimited options to the above reasons, which may affect all problems raised at the national level.

3.6. Environmental Challenges at the Local Level (of the city and its surroundings)

The main part of the environmental challenges arises from conditions rooted in national and international factors and imposed on cities, but the other part is related to relations, structures, or management of cities that must be founded in cities themselves; therefore, to properly analyze the conditions, the subject will be examined in the form of three areas of central, middle, and peripheral tissues. In the chart, two environmental challenges are described at the local and urban levels.

3.7. Iranian Environmental Challenges

Considering rivers, forests, pastures, wildlife, polluted water, soil, and air, species diversity, soil erosion, and pollution of resources, Iran is one of the most significant nations in terms of natural and environmental resources, covering 16,48,000 square kilometers. Iran's natural and environmental resources are vast and extensive. Figure 1 displays Iran's environmental performance metrics from 2006 to 2016.

Figure 1. Iran's Index of Environmental Performance (EPI) is based on rankings in the Environmental Performance Index [23].

With a geographical width of 37 and a longitude of 48, Iran is only the fifth most prosperous country globally. Among the valuable characteristics of this climate diversity and, accordingly, biodiversity is the country of Iran due to its 250 mm rainfall, which is equal to the global rain. Of the world's 17 climates, nine are related to Iran. If these measures are implemented, part of the country's problems will be solved.

3.8. Sustainable Development

Economists and social scientists believe that development means the continuous advancement of society and social order toward a better or more humane life. The 1987 report defines sustainable development as "that which satisfies the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to satisfy their own needs."

The report points out that legislation is needed to protect the environment and promote

development. The report also states that the goals must define sustainability in all countries, whether developed or developing [24]. Brundtland reports on the pressure of urban centers; as the world's urban populations are growing, they are expected to be ten times more in 80 years. In addition to developing countries, only 26% of the world's population consumes 80% of energy, steel, and other metals and paper [24].

Economic and Social Sciences define development as the continuous advancement of the whole of society and social order towards a better or more human life but as sustainable development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs [25]

Sustainable development combines two terms that combine two aspects of industrial economic growth and environmental quality into one symbol of sustainable development.

In other words, the two concepts of economics and ecology are joined together and form the basis of a sustainable development strategy [26]. What is in the definitions relating to joint sustainable development is its dynamic aspect, the elimination of basic needs, special attention to the protection of the environment and the prevention of its destruction and pollution, [27] A prerequisite for achieving sustainable development, efficiency in the allocation of liquids and sufficient condition is:

1. Reducing non-renewable resources and renewing and protecting them.
2. Replacing Renewable Resources with Renewed Resources.
3. balance the absorption of space by the environmentalist versus the amount of space added by the environmentalist [28].

Although natural resources have played a key role in shaping it from the beginning of the development plan, serious attention has ignored it until recent decades. The acceleration of economic growth during the Industrial Revolution was widely used by extracting natural resources to employ heavy industries, to the extent that the increasing black smoke from the factory fumes marked economic progress and modernization [29].

Table 3. Principles and Criteria for Sustainable Cities from the Viewpoint of [30].

Principles of Sustainable City	Criteria
More efficient use of land use	Development of park system Changing the concept of land
Fewer cars, better access	Mixed-use Access to public transportation Reduced demand for relocation
More efficient use of resources and less pollution	Recycle The polluter should pay
Improving the quality of housing and enhancing urban spaces	Designing houses and neighborhood units Improvement of public spaces in the city
Revitalization and revitalization of natural systems	Parks
Healthy community ecology	Fighting homelessness Fighting racial discrimination Empowering people

The concept of sustainability is rooted in an ecological principle based on the principle that if the natural capacity of environmental production, exploitation, or productivity is carried out

in any environment, the ecological resource capital principle remains sustainable, and human use of the environment is always sustainable.

Therefore, the amount of human consumption in a specific environment, which is in the capacity and capacity of the environment, has the maximum or maximum return because it is the size of the entire production.

In 1987, the Brent Land Commission launched a discussion on sustainability by publishing our Joint Future Report and international policies. Despite some criticism, this was the first credible definition of sustainable development. According to the report, the sustainable development of society must ensure that the needs of the present generation are met without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs.

Sustainable expansion requires meeting all basic needs and extending opportunities in such a way as to be able to share people's aspirations for a better life.

In the late 1980s, about 30 ecological and social design experts spent a week on the word sustainability and concluded that sustainability meant different responses to different fields. While the definition of sustainability still means that the use of energy and materials in an urban area is in balance with an area that can continuously through natural processes such as phonation, biological analysis, and biochemical processes that support life, these are also widely used [31].

In this fact, a sustainable ecological city, which has benefited from its area's natural resources to the extent necessary, is self-sufficient and makes sense to its inhabitants. Most of the residents of this city feel satisfied with living in this space.

Sustainable city foundations can be examined in seven sub-categories: sustainable urban economy, sustainable city community, sustainable urban access, sustainable urban life, and sustainable municipal population [29]

In the ultimate sense of environmental sustainability, environmental protection is for the survival of all communities in a just military and not the retention of existing status, in environmental benefits for the enjoyment of minorities of worldly people. Ecological sustainability is known as the building of sustainable development.

On this basis, the United Nations has declared that the most essential principle in planning is attention to the local conditions of the program. Land users must be given special attention for the sustainability of the boom areas because they play a vital role in the supply of water, energy, food, and green space.

Attention to natural hazards such as floods, earthquakes, droughts, fires, and... plays a vital role in shaping life. As a result, in cities today, environmental pollution, such as air pollution, noise, visual, resource degradation, and unwanted exploitation, is a symptom of ecological unsustainability [26].

4. Area of Study

The entire “Sari” city is geographically located at 53 degrees 3 minutes east and 36 degrees 34 minutes north. The city runs from east to city Neka, from west to city “Ghaem-Shahr,” from south to the Alborz Mountains, and from north to the Sea of Caspian. The city's height from the free sea level is 18/5 meters, and its distance to the coastline is 24 kilometers.

The city is the center of the province of Mazandaran and is on Tehran's trade and tourism path. It is located on the southeastern coast of the Caspian Sea and the northeastern cities of the country. Because of its political position, the administration has particular importance and credibility; it connects with Tehran and other provinces of the country by railway and asphalt.

Figure 1. Geographical location of the study area [32].

5. Research Findings

Today, cities are growing and expanding rapidly, absorbing the natural environments around them. The environmental challenges of urban settlements are the topics facing urban builders and policymakers today.

Urbanization has contributed to worsening social, cultural, and scientific conditions. Urbanization, population growth, and the effects of climate change on the environment are among the most urgent problems facing the world today.

These are the most important problems of the city today and their implications. It is a natural environment because urban development is necessarily accompanied by the domination of buildings, industries, transportation, and economic activities on natural spaces, which over time change in the form of urban displacement of nature and become the background of widespread urban pollution.

Urban development, population growth, the pursuit of greater prosperity, and a culture of unconsumable consumption, all extreme interference in nature, have disrupted the balance of the natural environment to such an extent that human life is at risk.

In Iran, as in other countries of the world, sustainable development has been emphasized with an emphasis on environmental conservation to deepen scientific and technical debate and to establish an authentic framework for making effective and efficient decisions in the country's durable development process, the High Council for Environmental Protection, an institution dedicated to the President of the Republic, approved the establishment of the National Committee for Sustainable Development on the 1933/09/08 [33].

The Green City Plan is one of the projects presented by the Environmental Protection Organization to the Green City Assembly on 1999/09/23.

One of the main objectives of this plan is to solve environmental problems and improve living conditions by raising public awareness and thus having a green space and a variety of pollution. Its subcomplex plans include green school plans, offices, and neighborhoods [34].

The main environmental threat of Iran, which threatens human security, can be explained below:

- Water: Iranian rainfall is dry land; the average annual rainfall is 250 mm, less than a third of the average worldwide, but predictions suggest that it will also be drier in the future. Water is Iran's most considerable resource shortage and the biggest long-term environmental threat. With the loss of groundwater resources, many parts of the country will become uncivilized, and its consequences will be devastating. The solution to the crisis will be a complete revision of the methods and approaches of water management in Iran. Many experts say it is necessary to fully understand the practices and approach to water management in Iran. Reinvented consideration. They offer four priorities:

- Participation
- Priced
- Protection

- Optimizing water use: This threat arises from deserts and deforestation. Water and watershed changes are causing desertification, but population pressure caused by excessive use of Beirut's water and water harvest also exacerbates the desert. The expansion rate of this disaster is so disturbing that it can make a large part of Iran uninhabitable.

- Energy: Iran's energy consumption and carbon dioxide production rate are among the highest in the world. This is related to Iran's growing population, legitimate aspirations for development, and abundant oil and natural gas reserves. Electricity and cheap energy have contributed significantly to this human development.

Still, for the government to decarbonize its economy, it must consider approaches that can include optimizing and efficient energy in consumer networks, increasing the share of solar, wave, blue, and geothermal energy, increasing participation of the private sector in the energy sector, in renewable energy, and investment in new energy technologies.

- Air pollution: Among all the environmental issues of Iran, the impact of air pollution on quality of life is likely to be the most dangerous and threatening. Statistics tell us that Iranian cities are among the most polluted cities in the world. The rainfall that began in the past year and then moved toward the western border of Iran increased air pollution. These storms are harming Iran's economy, especially agriculture, such as honey production and transportation; the Iranian biosystem, especially the blue forests in the Zagros Mountains, is threatening to solve the environmental problems in Iran, requiring a courageous approach from above.

5.1. The main causes of environmental challenges

- 1) Growth with minimal observation of the biological environment.
- 2) The value of natural goods and services.
- 3) Unable to implement the land plan.
- 4) Weakness of regulatory organizations in changing the use of millions of hectares+ About 150 plans do not have environmental impact assessments (EIA).
- 5) Shortage organizations in charge of the land.
- 6) The raw foodyism of nature.

5.2. The main reason for the water crisis

- 1) Low productivity in the agricultural sector.
- 2) 30-35% production efficiency.
- 3) Excessive consumption is caused by population growth (Population growth = water crisis).
 - i. 1956 = 19 million people.
 - ii. 1986 = 50 million people.
 - iii. 2016 = about 80 million people.
- 4) Withdrawal from underground water.
- 5) The number of authorized wells in 2013 was 455,000 rings, and the number of unauthorized Wells was between 100 and 150 thousand rings.
- 6) Permitted water extraction from wells in the year 2012 49/8 billion cubic meters.
- 7) Average reduction of underground water level = 18 meters.
- 8) Number plain of Country = 609 plain.
- 9) The number of forbidden planes with normal status = 228 plain (4/37%).
- 10) The number of forbidden planes with Critical situation = 66 plain (8/1%).
- 11) Water transfer projects.
 - i. Water transfers from sea to land.
 - ii. Transferring Persian Gulf water to 17 provinces of the Central Plateau (Minister of Energy, April 2016).
 - iii. Transfer of Caspian Sea water to Semnan.

6. Conclusions

Today, environmental challenges are among the most essential human concerns. This has increased concerns and complications.

Nowadays, environmental challenges are the most important human concerns. This has increased concerns about complications. Research shows that environmental challenges are rooted in various global, regional, and local factors. Iran, like many other countries.

Those with abundant natural resources have adopted a method of development that has put pressure on the acceptance of renewable resources. With its current practices of managing natural resources, Iran has faced warmer and drier futures, and environmental security in this geography is challenged. Unfortunately, the severe challenges of Iran's future are air pollution, drought, global warming, etc.

It must necessarily become an essential thought for the environment and natural resources of the country with a sustainable development approach and focus. The country's most significant environmental challenge is the water crisis; of course, it is not the shortage of water because we do not have the problem of water shortages, but the water management problem. If the country's water resources are appropriately managed, the water problem will be solved. The second problem is the round problem, which has no specific plan to solve. The gradual increase in air temperature, the continuous droughts of the years, and the burden of the exploitation of natural resources by the Bureau of Natural Resources have intensified this crisis. They focus on sustainability over a short period and durability over long periods. The difference between sustainability and sustainability indicators is that sustainability measures what's happening today, while sustainable development indicators measure the existing capacity for what will happen in the future.

Bio sustainability refers to a subset of Sustainable Development Goals that directly affect members of society. Biodiversity and sustainable development typically have common goals but often have multiple targets and priorities, both aimed at reducing pollution, while the sustainable focus is on the drivers that cause climate change. Bio-sustainability is focused on local air and noise contamination. Population growth in recent years has provided the ground for changes in the combination of urban and rural populations and has left a lot of detrimental effects on the urban environment.

These effects can be seen in various dimensions, such as violations of river safety, water quality, habitat, how waste is stored and collected and buried, noise pollution, energy consumption, and the state of natural resources, in ways that rapid urbanization and the development of equipment construction without planning and management can be considered as threats to the whole city.

A healthy environment, through the protection and improvement of human aging, provides conditions for human development. In the human development approach, environmental protection in economic growth is taken as the basis of sustainable development.

The primary sources of urban environmental pollutants are mainly household, industrial, over-solids, microbial, and chemical pollution. The rapid growth of the urban and urban populations has hindered the adoption of measures to protect the urban environment. The weakness of these measures is more apparent, especially in air pollution and inadequate compliance with environmental standards in urban settlements and noise.

Rapid urbanization, which directly creates environmental threats, has also contributed to environmental pollution by accelerating the development of industries in line with the increasing need to create jobs for migrants to cities. Examples of urban development of the whole town can be pointed out to the development of the city over the past few decades and the population growth of the town and its consequent expansion to the desired territory and to the infrastructure of the land over the various years, which has led to the creation of unsustainability in the process of city development.

The destruction of the surrounding gardens and agricultural land in the city continues to intensify. The increase in household waste, considering the amount of water produced to household income per year, results in an increased likelihood of water pollution by water pollutants and the loss of a significant volume of these resources, and two major factors of rapid population and urbanization growth on the one hand and industrial and agricultural development, on the other hand, have not only increased the need for freshwater but also provided areas for reduced water resources.

Entry into the freedom of rivers and beaches and construction of non-sustainable equipment, regardless of the sensitivity of the area's environment and pollution of surface waters, ultimately leads to the region's unsustainability.

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